

O‘ZBEKISTON DAVLAT SAN‘AT MUZEYINING BADIY HUNARMANDCHILIK KOLLEKSIYALARI TARIXIDAN

Sa’dullayeva Zamira Ravshan qizi, san‘atshunoslik fanlari bo‘yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), Toshkent Kimyo xalqaro universiteti dotsenti

ANNOTATSIYA

KIRISH: maqolada O‘zbekiston davlat san‘at muzeyi kolleksiyalari “O‘zbekiston xalq amaliy san‘ati” bo‘limi negizida ko‘rib chiqiladi. Tadqiqot markazida – XX asr O‘zbekiston badiiy hunarmandchiligi. Maqolada muzeydagi badiiy hunarmandchilik kolleksiyalarini hisobga olish tarixi va holati tadqiq etilgan. Doimiy ekspozitsiya o‘rganiladi va tahlil qilinadi. Fond ishining ilgari noma‘lum tomonlari, arxiv hujjatlari va hisob-kitob ma‘lumotlari ilk bor ilmiy muomalaga kiritildi. Xulosa o‘rnida, muallif o‘rganilgan ma‘lumotlar asosida aniqlangan muammolarni bartaraf etish bo‘yicha o‘zining uslubiy tavsiyalarini beradi.

MAQSAD: tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi O‘zbekiston davlat san‘at muzeyi “O‘zbekiston xalq amaliy san‘ati” bo‘limidagi XX asr badiiy hunarmandchilik kolleksiyalarining shakllanish tarixini o‘rganish, mavjud fond ashyolarining hisobga olinishi va saqlanish holatini tahlil qilish hamda ekspozitsiyadagi kamchiliklarni ilmiy asosda ochib berishdan iborat.

MATERIAL VA METODLAR: o‘zbekiston davlat san‘at muzeyi fondidagi 23 ta kolleksiya (kulolchilik, kashtachilik, kiyim-kechak, chitgarlik va b.), muzeyning ilmiy arxivi hujjatlari, inventar kitoblari hamda XX asrning 30-40-yillaridagi ilmiy ekspeditsiya hisobotlari. Maqolada tarixiy-qiyosiy tahlil, san‘atshunoslik va etnografik kuzatuv hamda muzeyshunoslikka oid tizimli tahlil metodlaridan foydalanilgan. Shuningdek, fond ashyolarining holati va arxiv ma‘lumotlarini ilmiy muomalaga kiritish orqali deskriptiv (tavsifiy) metod qo‘llanilgan.

NATIJA VA MUHOKAMALAR: muzey tarixi 1918-yildan emas, balki knyaz N.K.Romanovning shaxsiy kolleksiyasi asosida ancha ilgariroq boshlangani arxiv hujjatlari orqali isbotlandi. Kolleksiyalar tahlili: “O‘zbekiston kulolchiligi” kolleksiyasida 2500 ga yaqin ashyo borligi, ayniqsa, an‘analari yo‘qolib ketgan Kattaqo‘rg‘on kulolchilik maktabining 50 dan ortiq nodir namunalari saqlanishi aniqlandi. Muammolar: Kashtachilik va kiyim-kechak kolleksiyalarida hisobga olish ishlarida chalkashliklar (masalan, choyxaltalarning turli fondlarda takrorlanishi), ashyolarning saqlanish holati (kuya yegan paypoqlar) va eksponatlarni ko‘rgazmalarga haddan tashqari ko‘p chiqarish natijasida shikastlanishi kabi muammolar ochib berildi. Yangiliklar: Chitgarlik qoliplaridan nafaqat matoga, balki ipak sharflar va teri buyumlarga ham naqsh bosishda foydalanilgani birinchi bor qayd etildi.

XULOSA: muzey kolleksiyalari XX asr badiiy hunarmandchiligining barcha sohalarini (shisha, chinni, lokli miniatyura va b.) to‘liq qamrab olmagan, fondlarda tizimli uzilishlar mavjud. Muzey ekspozitsiyasi hali ham eski (tematik) uslubda bo‘lib, unda noan‘anaviy va sanoatlashgan hunarmandchilik namunalari e‘tibordan chetda qolmoqda. Fondagi chalkashliklarni bartaraf etish uchun ashyolarni qayta saralash, “Fondlarni

hisobga olish” bo’limi ishini takomillashtirish va kolleksiyalardagi bo’shliqlarni yangi eksponatlar bilan maqsadli to’ldirish zarur.

KALIT SO‘ZLAR: muzey, san’at, xalq hunarmandchiligi, kolleksiya, ijodkorlik, ekspozitsiya, fond ishlari, hisob-kitob hujjatlari, ekspeditsiya, an’ana, noan’anaviy, sanoat ijodkorligi.

ИЗ ИСТОРИИ КОЛЛЕКЦИЙ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННЫХ РЕМЕСЕЛ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОГО МУЗЕЯ ИСКУССТВ УЗБЕКИСТАНА

Саъдуллаева Замира Равшан кызы, доктор философии по искусствоведению (PhD), Доцент Ташкентского международного университета Кимё

АННОТАЦИЯ

ВВЕДЕНИЕ: в статье рассматривается коллекции Государственного музея искусств Узбекистана на базе отдела народно-прикладного искусства Узбекистана. В ракурсе автора – художественные ремесла Узбекистана XX века. Автор исследует историю и состоянию комплектования музейных коллекции по художественным ремеслам. Изучается и анализируется постоянная экспозиция. Вводится в научный оборот ранее неизвестные аспекты фоновой работы, архивные документы и сведения об учёте. В заключение, исходя из созданной картины, автор предлагает методические рекомендации для устранения выявленных проблем.

ЦЕЛЬ: основная цель исследования состоит в изучении истории формирования коллекций художественных ремёсел XX века в отделе «Народно-прикладное искусство Узбекистана» Государственного музея искусств Узбекистана. В задачи работы входит анализ состояния учёта и сохранности имеющихся фондовых предметов, а также научное обоснование и выявление недостатков в текущей экспозиции.

МАТЕРИАЛ И МЕТОДЫ: исследование базируется на 23 коллекциях фонда Государственного музея искусств Узбекистана, включая керамику, вышивку, одежду, набойку и другие виды искусств. Используются документы научного архива музея, инвентарные книги, а также отчёты научных экспедиций 30–40-х годов XX века. в статье применены методы историко-сравнительного анализа, искусствоведческого и этнографического наблюдения, а также системного анализа в области музееведения. Кроме того, использован дескриптивный (описательный) метод для введения в научный оборот архивных данных и сведений о состоянии фондовых экспонатов.

РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ И ОБСУЖДЕНИЕ: история музея: На основе архивных документов доказано, что история музея начинается значительно раньше 1918 года и связана с организацией частной коллекции князя Н. К. Романова. Установлено, что коллекция «Керамика Узбекистана» насчитывает около 2500 предметов, среди которых особую ценность представляют более 50 редких образцов ныне утраченной Каттакурганской школы керамики. Выявлены недостатки в системе учёта коллекций вышивки и одежды (например, дублирование учета чайхалта в разных фондах),

неудовлетворительное состояние сохранности некоторых предметов (изъеденные молью шерстяные изделия) и повреждение экспонатов из-за чрезмерно частого участия в выставках. Впервые зафиксировано, что формы для набойки (калыбы) использовались не только для тканей, но и для нанесения узоров на шелковые шарфы и кожаные изделия.

ЗАКЛЮЧЕНИЕ: коллекции музея не охватывают в полной мере все направления художественных ремёсел XX века (отсутствуют системные собрания по стеклу, фарфору, лаковой миниатюре и др.), наблюдаются хронологические разрывы. Музейная экспозиция по-прежнему следует устаревшему тематическому плану, в котором нетрадиционные и промышленные виды ремесла остаются без должного внимания. Для устранения выявленных проблем необходимо провести пересортицу предметов, усовершенствовать работу отдела учёта фондов и целенаправленно восполнить лакуны в коллекциях новыми экспонатами.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА: музей, искусство, народные ремёсла, коллекция, творчество, экспозиция, фондовая работа, документы учёта, экспедиция, традиция, нетрадиционная, промышленное творчество.

FROM THE HISTORY OF THE ARTISTIC HANDICRAFTS COLLECTIONS OF THE STATE ART MUSEUM OF UZBEKISTAN

Sadullaeva Zamira Ravshan kizi, Doctor of Philosophy in Art (PhD), Associate Professor at Kimyo International University in Tashkent

ANNOTATION

INTRODUCTION: the article discusses the collections of the State Museum of Art of Uzbekistan on the basis of the department of national applied art of Uzbekistan. From the perspective of the author - the artistic crafts of Uzbekistan of the twentieth century. The author explores the history and state of acquisition of museum collections for artistic crafts. Studied and analyzed permanent exposure. Previously unknown aspects of the background work, archival documents and accounting information are introduced into the scientific circulation. In conclusion, based on the created picture, the author offers methodological recommendations for eliminating the identified problems.

AIM: the primary aim of the research is to study the history of the formation of 20th-century artistic craft collections within the "National Applied Art of Uzbekistan" department of the State Museum of Art of Uzbekistan. The study aims to analyze the current state of accounting and preservation of fund items, as well as to scientifically identify and highlight deficiencies in the permanent exposition.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: the research is based on 23 collections from the funds of the State Museum of Art of Uzbekistan, including ceramics, embroidery, clothing, and block printing. It utilizes scientific archive documents, inventory books, and reports from scientific expeditions conducted in the 1930s and 1940s. The article employs methods of historical-comparative analysis, art historical and ethnographic observation, and systematic analysis within the field of museology. Additionally, a descriptive method

is used to introduce archival data and information regarding the physical condition of fund items into scientific circulation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION: museum History: Based on archival documents, it is proven that the history of the museum begins significantly earlier than 1918, rooted in the private collection of Prince N.K. Romanov. Collection Analysis: It was determined that the "Ceramics of Uzbekistan" collection contains approximately 2,500 items, including over 50 rare specimens from the Kattaqurgan pottery school, whose traditions have since been lost. Issues: Discrepancies were found in the accounting of embroidery and clothing collections (e.g., the misplacement of tea bags across different funds). Problems regarding the preservation of items (such as moth-damaged wool products) and the damage of exhibits due to excessive transport for external exhibitions were also highlighted. Innovation: It was recorded for the first time that block printing molds (qoliplar) were used not only for textiles but also for applying patterns to silk scarves and leather goods.

CONCLUSION: the museum collections do not fully encompass all sectors of 20th-century artistic crafts, with systematic gaps in areas such as artistic glass, porcelain, and lacquer miniature. The museum exposition still adheres to an outdated thematic plan that overlooks non-traditional and industrialized craft sectors. To eliminate identified problems, it is necessary to re-sort items, improve the work of the "Fund Accounting" department, and purposefully fill collection gaps with new acquisitions.

Keywords: museum, art, folk crafts, collection, creativity, exposition, fund work, accounting documents, expedition, tradition, non-traditional, industrial creativity.

The State Art Museum of Uzbekistan was established in 1918 based on the transfer of the collection of Grand Duke Nikolay Konstantinovich Romanov (1850–1918) to state ownership (8, p. 7). The Central State Archive of Uzbekistan holds a collection of documents pertaining to the chancellery of Prince N. K. Romanov (20). These documents indicate that during his lifetime, the Prince purchased numerous works of art related to Russia, Western Europe, and Eastern countries at auctions in Russia and Europe. He organized this collection as an exhibition in his home and invited the local population to view these samples of world art every Friday. His three-story house in Tashkent, built in 1891 by Wilhelm Salomonovich Heintzelmann (1851–1922) and Alexey Leontievich Benois (1838–1902) using greyish-yellow fired brick and featuring a basement, was intended for exhibitions from the very beginning. If we rely on these archival documents, the history of the Art Museum of Uzbekistan begins not in 1918, but much earlier.

Throughout its history, the museum has operated under the authority of various institutions and has not always had a permanent building. Initially, it functioned as the Museum of the People's University, then the Central Art Museum; from 1924, it became the Tashkent Art Museum, and from 1935, the State Art Museum of Uzbekistan. From 1918 to 1935, it was located in the aforementioned Prince's house, and after 1935, it moved to other premises. In 1948, it was housed in a two-story building in Tashkent named after Kafanov (architect V. S. Heintzelmann).

In 1974, that building was demolished, and a new, cube-shaped structure was built in its place (architects I. Abdulov, A. Nikiforov, S. Rozenblyum). The building was covered on all four sides with stained-glass windows, which were not ordinary glass. The architects, taking into account the local climatic conditions, ordered special glass that would not allow the heat of the sun's rays to pass through. However, during renovations in the 1990s, these windows were replaced with new ones, and the sides were covered with Alucobond from the outside. As a result, the architectural and artistic image originally proposed by the architects was somewhat compromised.

Rich samples of 20th-century Uzbek artistic crafts are kept in 23 collections belonging to the "Applied Arts of the People of Uzbekistan" department of the museum.

It is worth noting that the museum carried out its primary activities in terms of collecting items between 1935 and 1940. For example, in 1935, a scientific expedition involving architect S. P. Polupanov and photographer I. P. Zavalin visited Samarkand to scientifically study monuments of folk architecture and brought back samples of ceramic tiles to the museum (12). Professor M. S. Andreev (4) and ethnographer A. K. Pisarchik (10) traveled to Bukhara and Khorezm in 1936, and to Nurata and Margilan in 1937, to shape the collection of folk applied arts. In 1938, museum staff participated in an archaeological expedition led by V. A. Shishkin at the Varakhsha Palace, organized by the "Uzkomstaris" committee. In the same year, museum researcher N. V. Rusinova was sent to Bukhara to collect items for the "Molds" (Qoliblar) collection (14). In 1940, archaeologist G. V. Parfenov was sent to Zarautsoy to study the culture of the primitive era and to make copies of rock paintings (9). In 1941, N. V. Rusinova (13) was sent to Urgut to collect molds, and V. S. Zatzornitskaya (5) was sent to Fergana to collect engraved metal and copperware. These employees had different specialties: architects, ethnographers, historians, and orientalists. For this reason, those collections were formed not according to a pre-developed precise scientific plan, but based on items acquired during initial encounters.

The "Uzbek Ceramics" collection in the museum stands out for its diversity and rich composition, making it unique not only among museums in the republic but also among other collections in the world dedicated to Uzbek ceramics of the 19th and 20th centuries. In total, it houses about 2,500 ceramic items, with the core of the collection consisting of exhibits from the 20th century. It includes the artistic characteristics of ceramic schools that were active in Uzbekistan in the 20th century, as well as the works of masters who worked effectively in the centers based on these schools. The collection also contains pieces of architectural tiles, collected by architect S. P. Polupanov in 1935, which are stored in about six wooden crates but have not yet been sufficiently studied by specialists.

One of the most unique ceramic collections is the work of Katta-Kurgan potters such as Usta Shoboboev and Usta Hidoyat, who worked at the beginning of the 20th century. Katta-Kurgan ceramics are extremely valuable to us because the traditions of this center have completely disappeared today. The museum preserves over 50 plates by Katta-Kurgan masters; this collection was registered in two stages. In the first stage, 41 plates were purchased from the Samarkand Museum of Crafts in 1935. In the second stage, 10

plates were purchased based on orders from the Minister of Culture of the Uzbek SSR: 1) Order No. 130 dated June 23, 1961; 2) Order No. 150 dated December 28, 1965. The first batch of exhibits was studied and documented with scientific passports by A. S. Morozova in 1948–1959. N. Azizova and A. K. Pisarchik wrote scientific passports for the second batch of exhibits.

Another reason we are paying special attention to the examples of Katta-Kurgan ceramics is the necessity to restore the traditions of this defunct ceramic center based on the samples in the museum.

Another important aspect of the collection is that it primarily consists of works by masters who worked in the traditional direction of Uzbek ceramics. However, it should be noted that in the 20th century, alongside the traditional direction, industrialized and professional (non-traditional) artistic crafts also developed in Uzbekistan (17). Therefore, this period is rich in new experiments and discoveries and is considered one of the brightest periods in the history of artistic crafts and decorative applied arts.

The creative pursuits of non-traditional potters—Mukhitdin Rakhimov (1903–1985) from Tashkent, Abdurahim Mukhtarov from Samarkand, and Sofya Rakova (1919–2003)—have found a worthy place in the museum's collection. While M. Rakhimov, in his creative research, experimentally recreated images and motifs from Afrasiyab ceramics or items found during other archaeological excavations, S. Rakova sought to create national types characteristic of the era in which she lived. Abdurahim Mukhtarov, in turn, created a collection of narrative thematic figurines, which had been initiated by Umar Jurakulov.

Although such experimental works by the master were considered non-traditional at the time, half a century later, the research of M. Rakhimov and S. Rakova remained as non-traditional as before. However, A. Mukhtarov's thematic figurines were embraced with great interest by the next generation of masters, and they have now taken their place among traditional ceramics.

The earthquake that occurred in August 2008 caused significant, albeit manageable, damage to the halls and the repository of the State Art Museum of Uzbekistan. Marble pieces covering the columns in the foyer fell off. Parts of the ceilings in the exhibition halls were also damaged. Several wall-mounted exhibits from the eighth hall fell and shattered into pieces. Fortunately, in the museum's storage facility No. 3, where the Uzbek ceramics are kept, the items were stacked closely together on shelves, which prevented them from being damaged; otherwise, the situation in the storage area would have been dire.

On August 22, 2008, a commission consisting of Svetlana Manasyan (Deputy Director for Research), Mirfayzi Usmanov (Chief Curator), Ravshan Fatkhullaev (Head of the "Folk Applied Arts of Uzbekistan" department), gallery attendants Nina Kashina and Saodat Kodirova, restorer Bakhtiyor Botirov, and police officer Alisher Azizov documented that, as a result of the earthquake, a human military statue from the Khalchayan sculpture collection had broken and crumbled, and a plate by Samarkand potter Umar Jurakulov (KK No. 17923, Inv. No. 1709) in the eighth hall had split in two. The damaged items were

handed over to the Chief Curator for restoration (see: Museum Director's Order No. 27-P dated August 28, 2008).

The museum's second most unique collection consists of artistic embroidery. According to inventories from 2007–2009, there are 1,822 embroidery samples. Items such as *choyshab* (bedspreads), *gulko'ra* (decorative quilts), and *sozanas* testify to the exquisite taste of embroiderers from all the embroidery schools of Uzbekistan. Unfortunately, a review of the documentation for this collection revealed that many errors were made in the past regarding proper inventory management. Furthermore, since the 1980s, the "Restoration Workshop" in the museum has fallen short of required standards, resulting in many embroideries needing repair. Additionally, it makes little sense that the rarest items in the collection—particularly *sozanas*, bedspreads, and quilts from Bukhara, Shakhrisabz, and Tashkent—were repeatedly taken for foreign exhibitions, displays at the Exhibition of Achievements of the National Economy (VDNKh) in Tashkent, or exhibitions organized at Tashkent restaurants for high-ranking foreign guests.

The collection also contains items of an ethnographic nature, such as "tea bags," "mirror bags," and "money pouches," which have received little attention from specialists in scientific research and exhibitions. This is because, in the museum's history, staff members conducting expeditions carried out their collection work based on methods of ethnographic research rather than art history. While many of these are small bags featuring the "iroqi" stitch common in Shakhrisabz embroidery, there are also unique specimens, such as those from Nurata in the early 20th century, decorated with intricate, tiny blue beads (KK No. 7611, Inv. No. 27). We identified an inventory issue here: some embroidered items were registered in the "Clothing" collection, while others were placed in the "Embroidery" collection. If the embroideries that are part of garments remain in the "Clothing" collection and the rest are transferred to the "Embroidery" collection, the archive would be much better organized. This would be helpful for scientific research, rapid sorting of items, and the preparation of catalogs. Museum practice often demands the unexpected organization of exhibitions during the visits of heads of state, requiring staff to work operationally in a very short time.

The museum's repository also contains a small number of non-traditional embroidery samples alongside the traditional ones. A case in point is the portrait of Alisher Navoi (1441–1501) embroidered by Tashkent master Fazilat Saydalieva. The poet's portrait was embroidered in colored thread on canvas stretched over a wooden frame, based on a painting by People's Artist of Uzbekistan V. Kaydalov (1907–1985). Such embroidery, created using tapestry techniques, appeared in Uzbekistan in the 20th century and did not exist previously. Inspired by such works of art common in Russian and European decorative arts, the Tashkent embroiderer skillfully created the poet's portrait and manually embroidered fragments of Navoi's verses in Arabic script around the frame. The initiative started by Fazilat Saydalieva in embroidery was continued by later generations of embroiderers in tapestry and other fields of artistic crafts.

Another unique collection of the Art Museum is the clothing collection. This set includes two sub-collections that are particularly interesting to specialists. One is the

collection of *paranjis* (traditional cloaks), and the other is the collection of *peshikurtas* (decorative ribbon-like collar ornaments for traditional women's dresses).

Unfortunately, due to a lack of exhibition space, only one of the unique *paranjis* dating back to the early 20th century is on display. It should be noted that the artistic value of this particular *paranji* is not very high and it appears quite modest compared to those stored in the repository; it is made of black velvet. The *paranji* is displayed with its *chachvon* (face veil) to give visitors a holistic impression of the outer garments worn by local women in the recent past. The *chachvon* is woven from horsehair and decorated with three-sided *yorma* (chain stitch) embroidery.

The museum possesses a unique collection of *jiyaks* (braided trim). In Uzbekistan, the main centers of traditional *jiyak* making were Tashkent, Fergana, Namangan, Samarkand, and Shakhrisabz. They are used as parts of traditional costumes, or as decorations for women's trousers (*lozim*) and skullcaps (*doppi*). They are called "jiyak" in Fergana, Tashkent, and Samarkand, and "zeh" in Bukhara. *Jiyaks* are usually not sewn onto the fabric cut for the garment; rather, they are crafted separately and then stitched onto the necessary parts of the clothing (16, p. 2).

The collection has been covered in the scientific research of art historians and ethnographers in various periods. Among those known to us, the most significant are the scientific works published by Gisela Dobrovsky (a former researcher at the Ethnographic Museum in Berlin) (1), and Uzbek scholars Nina Avedova (2), Nadejda Rusinova (14), and Ravshan Fatkhullaev (19).

Another collection similar to the *jiyaks* (braided trim) is that of the *peshikurtas* (decorative ribbon-like collar ornaments for traditional women's dresses). The "Clothing" collection houses a total of 108 unique specimens: 54 from Shakhrisabz (early 20th century), 33 from Nurata, and the remainder from Tajikistan and Bukhara. Among them, those of the highest artistic quality were undoubtedly crafted by Shakhrisabz embroiderers. These include pieces worked in the *iroqi* stitch featuring motifs such as the "amulet," "pitcher," "mihrab," and wise sayings in Arabic script.

The "Clothing" collection contains items that have already reached the end of their service life and have lost their quality; they currently hold neither artistic nor scientific value. I am referring to more than 50 pairs of wool-knitted socks and gloves for men and women. These were collected from the Tajik population living in the mountainous regions of the Pamirs. They were acquired by Professor Mikhail Stepanovich Andreev (1873–1948) during his 1925 expedition, which followed the route: Tashkent – Istaravshan (Ura-Tyube) – Zarafshan Valley – Yangob – Anzob Pass – Dushanbe – Karategin – Darvaz – Pamir Valley – Pamir – Osh (13). These items were hand-knitted from wool and are knee-high. The reason these items ended up in the museum is that in those years, what is now the "Folk Applied Arts of Uzbekistan" department was called the "Central Asian Applied Arts Department." Therefore, M. S. Andreev also carried out collecting work in territories outside of Uzbekistan.

Because this collection was left unattended for years, all the items were riddled with moth holes. Some were reduced to mere fragments. In 2008, during the transfer of the

collection from one curator to another, the items were taken out of the disinfection chamber, and each was compared one by one with the records in the inventory book. Prior to this, they had been stored unattended in household goods boxes, heavily treated with DDT powder.

The inventory book had these socks entered as a single pair under one registration number, marked as (a) and (b). From today's perspective, this is incorrect, as only one item should be entered under a single registration number (7). During the transfer, curator R. S. Fatkhullaev and the receiver, M. H. Tojiddinova, compared each pair of socks with their individual inventory records, individually wrapped them in paper, and labeled them with their respective registration numbers. At the conclusion of the transfer process, the commission recommended that the museum administration remove these exhibits from the registry.

In this collection, there are other rarities besides the Shakhrisabz *peshikurtas* stitched in *iroqi*. I am referring to a *peshikurta* (KK No. 21248, Inv. No. 858) named "Setora" (Persian for "star"), prepared in the 20th century in the Shorchi district of the Surkhandarya region. As mentioned, a *peshikurta* is a decorative collar ornament for women's dresses. It adorns the front of the dress. The whole ribbon hanging downward splits into two when it reaches the chest, joining the seam at the shoulder of the garment. While other *peshikurtas* were stitched in the *iroqi* style, the base of this one is a cotton ribbon adorned with round metal plates. The star shape was embossed onto them. Since the design was struck from the back of the plate, the pattern protrudes on the front.

In its current state, all the plates on the *peshikurta* are in place, but one of the six tassels hanging from the bottom is missing. The top part of the ribbon has been damaged by moths. Based on a formal report, the collection curator handed this exhibit to the museum's Chief Curator for restoration.

During the transfer of the "Clothing" collection, several previous errors were identified and corrected to ensure that the collection inventory is maintained without flaws. For instance, consider the "Tea Bag" (Inv. No. 20) in the "Clothing" collection, made from a red satin base and decorated with free-flowing patterns in "yorma" (chain stitch). It has seven tassels around the edge.

It turns out that a similar tea bag was entered into the "Embroidery" collection's inventory book, also under number 20. The staff discovered this coincidence while comparing the items to their scientific descriptions in the inventory book. They realized the item was in its place, but the scientific description in the collection book did not match the actual appearance of the item.

Conversely, the tea bag from the "Clothing" collection had ended up in the cabinet where the tea bag from the "Embroidery" collection was kept, causing the two items to be swapped. The commission got to the bottom of this issue and provided the necessary recommendations to the "Fund Inventory" department.

One of the most unique and currently relevant collections of Uzbek artistic crafts is that of *chitgarlik* (block printing). The collection holds 115 unique samples prepared in Khorezm, Bukhara, Samarkand, Tashkent, Gijduvan, and Margilan. It should be noted that

throughout the entire 20th century—even in the 1950s and 60s—block printing was valued by both rural and urban populations for its affordability and aesthetic significance. Unfortunately, this art entered a crisis by the 1990s. The older generation of masters passed away, generations changed, and in the new era, demand dropped as it could not compete with imported block-printed goods. As a result, children did not continue the family craft and moved into other fields.

The artistic value of the collection lies in the fact that it fully captures the distinct characteristics of fabrics created in various Uzbek centers of block printing. While three colors—red, green, and black—predominated in Tashkent and Fergana (KK No. 14599, Inv. No. 83; KK No. 16633, Inv. No. 89; KK No. 7762, Inv. No. 29), black and indigo shades were used in Khorezm (KK No. 5926, Inv. No. 2; KK No. 5926, Inv. No. 8; KK No. 59264, Inv. No. ?), and multi-colored dyes were utilized in Bukhara and Samarkand (KK No. 12970, Inv. No. 80; KK No. 3426, Inv. No. 20; KK No. 20706, Inv. No. 96).

The field of block printing, more than other areas of folk crafts, is closely intertwined with another craft: the creation of printing blocks. The State Art Museum of Uzbekistan holds a unique collection of over 1,400 such blocks. The collection was initiated by Professor Mikhail Stepanovich Andreev (1873–1948), who purchased the first 130 samples during the museum's ethnographic and art history expeditions to Bukhara and Khiva in 1936, and to Nurata and Margilan in 1937. In subsequent years, specifically between 1936 and 1941, additional large batches of blocks were registered into the museum (15, p. 1).

The work during this period was carried out by N. V. Rusinova, a student of Professor M. S. Andreev, who worked as a researcher at the museum in the 1930s. The scholar's expeditions took place during the years of the Second World War (8). To preserve magnificent samples of folk decorative art, N. Rusinova dedicated five years to significant work in studying the methods of block printing on cotton fabric (*chitgarlik*) and collecting pattern samples. After the scholar's untimely death, the collection items were organized, and in the 1970s and 1980s, subsequent generations of specialists wrote scientific passports for them (18, p. 46).

In research conducted until recently, there was a prevailing view that these blocks were used exclusively in block printing (*chitgarlik*) (2, 3). However, a careful study of the museum's collection revealed that, in their time, they were also used to print patterns on women's silk scarves. The collection even contains four blocks that were used to apply designs to leather chests and boxes (KK No. 20080, Inv. No. 1417; KK No. 20078, Inv. No. 1419; KK No. 20079, Inv. No. 1418; KK No. 20077, Inv. No. 1420).

The museum also houses demonstrative copies of block patterns (Inv. No. 69/28), which were intentionally prepared in advance by the masters to show potential customers as samples.

One of the museum's unique collections is that of artistic textiles. It contains over a thousand rare hand-woven items. Throughout the 20th century, the collection gathered not only items woven in domestic settings but also samples produced in textile mills based on special sketches by artists. An example of this can be seen in the collaborative works of

artists A. Golubev, F. Povtsyaniy, and colorist N. Malyshev, produced at the Tashkent Textile Factory in 1937–1938. These works make extensive use of motifs from traditional Uzbek *sozanas*, architectural decoration, and the "cotton flower" (*paxtagul*) pattern—an ornamental motif famous in all artistic fields during the Soviet era.

From the above, it can be concluded that the State Art Museum of Uzbekistan, unfortunately, could not fully cover all branches of Uzbek artistic crafts throughout the 20th century. The existing collections have systematic gaps.

Collections for certain fields that developed rapidly during the 20th century were never created, such as artistic glass, rare souvenir items produced at the Tashkent Porcelain Factory, Uzbek lacquer miniatures, and non-traditional artistic crafts such as tapestries, artistic porcelain, and non-traditional ceramics.

Throughout the museum's century-long history, the permanent exhibition has, unfortunately, continued to repeat the thematic exhibition plan established in the former Kafanov club. The primary method used there focused on displaying each field separately, with the emphasis placed solely on traditional craft sectors.

The non-traditional and industrialized artistic craft sectors of the 20th century remained outside the view of the exhibition's creators. If these issues are included in the museum's future plans, and if the gaps in the collections are purposefully filled with new exhibits, the museum would be able to fully represent the artistic crafts and decorative applied arts of Uzbekistan, including those currently held in storage.

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